

MODERN TECHNOLOGIES FOR IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF ELECTRICITY

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Annotation. *The technological processes of any production largely depend on the quality of electricity. In general, poor quality of electricity can be characterized as any changes in the power supply that lead to disruptions in the normal course of the production process or damage to equipment, transformers, electric motors. In this article, only transmission and distribution are considered, since these points show a growing tendency to interpenetrate due to the development of decentralized electricity production. We will focus on the issues of voltage quality. Of course, in this form, the description will be incomplete, since the continuity of power supply is also one of the main parameters of the general concept of electricity quality.*

Key words: *overhead power lines, monitoring, ice methods and devices for icing control, overhead lines, reinsurance and proactive.*

Due to the considerable length of overhead power lines, they are exposed to atmospheric phenomena. Various types of atmospheric electricity discharges (lightning) are the causes of various types of disturbances, throws, landings of mains voltage, complete power outage. The duration and degree of disturbances depend on the network structure and the time required for its reconfiguration. The causes of overvoltage due to lightning strikes are usually considered as external to the network. Other types of disturbances occur during network management, during resets or unexpected increases in load. Although the latter type of disturbances is quite rare, since usually large loads are connected to the network gradually. This does not apply to sudden load drops, which are often the result of accidents. In-network sources of disturbances. Now we are dealing with an increasing number of

electrical loads that degrade the quality of energy in the grid both at the household and industrial level, and with active activities to standardize energy quality.

The latter trend is very ambiguous, since at the initial stage it leads to penalties against manufacturers and even consumers, while organizations engaged in energy distribution, as a rule, do not bear any responsibility regarding the short-circuit power or the total resistance structure of the network. Power electronics causes a deterioration in energy quality, but compared to other types of conversion, it is characterized by its own means of combating this deterioration,

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

Longitudinal compensation. High voltage lines have an inductive resistance, and the higher the voltage drop on it, the higher the transport angle. The idea of increasing the transmitted power is simple. The value of the inductive resistance must be compensated by a series-connected capacitance. Currently, several design solutions are used. Constant capacitance capacitor (Fig. 1)

Figure 1. Capacitor bank with thyristor switching

Figure 2. Capacitor bank with thyristor control

Figure 3. Capacitor bank with thermistor control

The degree of compensation is constant. This principle makes it possible to increase the power transmitted through the line until the heat dissipation limits are reached. Such systems are not capable of suppressing the occurrence of sub synchronous oscillations of power plant generators, on the contrary, with this method of compensation, conditions favorable for their occurrence can be created. Capacitor bank with thermistor switching (Fig. 2). The degree of compensation varies stepwise. All the comments to the solution in Figure 1 remain valid for this solution as well. Capacitor bank with thruster control (Fig. 3) The degree of compensation is regulated within almost any limits. Transverse compensation. A device connected to the middle point of the line and capable of absorbing and returning reactive power ensures constant voltage at this point. In this case, the transport angle is reduced by half and, accordingly, the transmitted power can be increased. Such devices were developed more than 30 years ago. The solution consists in connecting a capacitance to the line, and in parallel to it – an adjustable device capable of compensating for excess reactive power to maintain a constant voltage value at the connection point (Fig. 4)

V_s – source voltage;

V_a – receiver voltage;

X – a reactor having a purely inductive resistance. **Phase-shifting transformer. The angle (between voltages) is the most important parameter of power regulation (Fig. 6).**

Figure 6. How FACTS works.

STATCOM compensators can also behave like active filters. Of course, you have to pay extra for the additional functionality of STATCOM compensators.

Among the many functions of these compensators , the following are classic:

- voltage regulation by absorbing or returning reactive power;
- suppression of sub synchronous oscillations.

III. CONCLUSION

To stabilize the voltage of distribution networks, the same means are used as in transmission networks, although the purposes of their application are somewhat different. The question arises about voltage control and increasing the power factor. Difficulties mainly arise due to rapidly changing loads, such as rolling mills, welding units and, most of all, arc furnaces. Figure 5 shows a typical example of a generalized distribution network with disturbances that are eliminated by installing an SVC. The figure shows the capacitors installed as part of the filters for harmonic suppression;

the capacitance of the capacitors is selected in such a way as to return the reactive power necessary to maintain the set value of $\text{tg } \varphi$; there is also an absorber (TCR-choke with thruster control) designed to compensate for excess capacitance in necessary cases. Electric power transmission and distribution networks are one of the most important keys to the future. The quality of electricity is largely related to the processes of its transmission and distribution. It is a critical parameter for modern production. The development of electric networks all over the world, the growth in the number of interconnections impose new requirements for reliability, security, and especially for the quality of energy flow management. To meet these requirements of the XXI century, modern tools are emerging both at the project level and at the level of ready-made equipment.

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